

FROM ALGORITHM TO LESSON PLAN: INTEGRITY, ACCOUNTABILITY AND LEARNING OUTCOMES OF AI-ASSISTED TOOLS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN CROSS RIVER STATE

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

This study examined the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction and their effects on integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and involved a population of 5,302 teachers and 77,485 students. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 770 respondents (372 teachers and 398 students) was selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using mean scores and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The findings revealed that the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction was moderate among teachers and was similarly perceived by students. The study also found that AI-assisted tools have a moderate positive effect on integrity and accountability in teaching and learning, and a moderate positive effect on students' learning outcomes. Pearson correlation results indicated significant positive relationships between the use of AI-assisted tools and the quality of lesson delivery ($r = 0.46$; $p < 0.05$), integrity and accountability ($r = 0.41$; $p < 0.05$), and students' learning outcomes ($r = 0.44$; $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that AI-assisted tools have the potential to improve teaching quality, promote integrity and accountability, and enhance students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools. However, the integration of AI tools is constrained by limited access, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient training. The study recommended improved ICT infrastructure, teacher training, ethical guidelines for AI use, and effective monitoring mechanisms to enhance AI adoption and maximize its benefits in secondary education

KEYWORDS: AI-assisted tools, lesson planning, integrity, accountability, learning outcomes, public secondary schools, Cross River State.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-assisted tools into educational settings has accelerated globally, reshaping instructional strategies, learning experiences, and educational outcomes. Innovations such as adaptive learning platforms, automated assessment systems, AI-driven tutoring applications, and intelligent feedback mechanisms have gained traction for

their potential to personalize learning and support both teachers and students (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019). These technologies are viewed as catalysts for improving access to quality education and supporting differentiated instruction in diverse contexts (UNESCO, 2021).

In Nigeria, the adoption of AI-assisted tools in education is still emerging, particularly within public secondary schools. The educational sector faces significant challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited digital literacy among teachers, and insufficient funding for technology integration (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). While the Federal Ministry of Education has made efforts to integrate ICT in schools, the use of AI-driven tools remains minimal due to uneven access to electricity, internet connectivity, and educational technology resources (Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). Despite these limitations, teachers and educational stakeholders show increasing interest in leveraging AI to improve teaching efficiency and student learning outcomes (Fokam, 2020; Ndukwe & Odu, 2022).

In Cross River State, public secondary schools face similar challenges, including teacher shortages, large class sizes, and inadequate instructional materials. These issues constrain effective lesson delivery and learning achievement, making the potential benefits of AI-assisted tools highly relevant. However, the use of AI in lesson planning and instruction is not yet widely documented, creating a gap in understanding how AI tools affect teaching quality and student performance in the state (Cross River State Ministry of Education, 2023).

The use of AI in education also raises concerns about integrity and accountability, which are crucial in ensuring responsible technology adoption. Integrity issues arise when AI tools influence assessment practices, academic honesty, and fairness in student evaluation (Selwyn, 2019; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2021). Automated grading systems, for instance, may be prone to bias or inaccuracies, affecting the reliability of assessment outcomes (Baker & Smith, 2019). Accountability concerns involve transparency in AI algorithms, ethical use of data, and responsibility for educational decisions made using AI tools (Eynon, 2020; OECD, 2021). Without clear policies and monitoring mechanisms, AI adoption could unintentionally compromise academic standards, widen disparities, and undermine trust in educational institutions.

Understanding the relationship between AI-assisted tools, pedagogical processes, and learning outcomes in Cross River State's public secondary schools is therefore essential. Current literature indicates that AI can enhance instructional quality and learning outcomes when integrated responsibly, but it can also reinforce existing inequalities if not properly managed (Luckin et al., 2016; UNESCO, 2021). There is limited empirical evidence documenting how AI tools influence lesson planning, teaching effectiveness, and student achievement within Cross River State, particularly regarding ethical implications and accountability frameworks.

Consequently, this study explores the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction, focusing on integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The study aims to provide evidence-based insights that can guide teachers, policymakers, and stakeholders in harnessing AI responsibly to improve teaching and learning.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies has introduced new opportunities for improving teaching and learning in educational systems worldwide. AI-assisted tools such as adaptive learning platforms, automated assessment systems, and intelligent tutoring applications offer potential benefits in lesson planning, instructional delivery, and student support. However, the integration of these tools into public secondary schools in Cross River State remains limited and poorly documented. This situation raises concerns about how AI is being adopted, the extent to which it is aligned with educational goals, and its impact on learning outcomes.

Moreover, the use of AI in education introduces critical issues related to integrity and accountability. AI tools may inadvertently facilitate academic dishonesty, such as cheating, plagiarism, and manipulation of assessment results, particularly when systems are used without proper supervision and ethical guidelines (Selwyn, 2019; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2021). The lack of clear policies and monitoring mechanisms in schools can result in inconsistent application of AI technologies, thereby undermining the fairness and credibility of the educational process (Eynon, 2020; OECD, 2021). Additionally, AI systems may exhibit algorithmic biases that disadvantage certain groups of students, leading to inequitable learning opportunities and outcomes (Holmes et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2021).

In Cross River State, public secondary schools often face infrastructural challenges such as inadequate electricity supply, limited internet access and insufficient technological resources, which hinder effective adoption of AI-assisted tools (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). Furthermore, many teachers lack the necessary digital literacy and training to integrate AI into lesson planning and instructional practice effectively (Ndukwe & Odu, 2022). Consequently, there is limited evidence on how AI tools influence teaching quality, student engagement, and academic achievement within the state.

Therefore, the problem addressed in this study is the uncertainty surrounding the integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes associated with the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction in public secondary schools in Cross River State. Without empirical data and clear governance frameworks, policymakers and educators may struggle to harness AI effectively, potentially exacerbating existing educational challenges rather than improving them.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction in public secondary schools in Cross River State.
2. To determine the impact of AI-assisted tools on integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State.
3. To assess the effect of AI-assisted tools on learning outcomes of students in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Research Questions

1. What is the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction in public secondary schools in Cross River State?

2. How do AI-assisted tools affect integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State?
3. What is the effect of AI-assisted tools on students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and the quality of lesson delivery in public secondary schools in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant relationship between AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State.
3. There is no significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Literature Review

AI-Assisted Tools in Lesson Planning and Instruction in Public Secondary Schools in Cross River State

Artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted tools are digital technologies that use algorithms and data analytics to support teaching, learning, and assessment processes (Luckin et al., 2016). These tools include adaptive learning platforms, automated grading systems, intelligent tutoring applications, and AI-based content generation tools that can aid teachers in lesson planning and instructional delivery (Holmes et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2021). In public secondary schools in Cross River State, the adoption of AI-assisted tools remains limited and uneven, largely due to infrastructural challenges such as unreliable electricity supply, limited internet connectivity, and inadequate technological resources (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). Additionally, many teachers in the state lack adequate digital literacy and professional training to effectively integrate AI tools into their instructional practices, which further constrains the use of such technologies in lesson planning (Ndukwe & Odu, 2022).

Despite these challenges, there is a growing interest among educators in using AI-assisted tools to improve teaching efficiency and enhance learning outcomes. AI tools can support lesson planning by generating instructional materials, suggesting learning activities, and providing data-driven insights into students' performance and learning needs (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019). However, the integration of AI in classrooms also raises concerns regarding integrity and accountability, especially when AI tools are used for assessment and grading. Without proper guidelines, AI systems may contribute to academic dishonesty, such as cheating and plagiarism, and may reinforce bias or unfair practices in student evaluation (Selwyn, 2019; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2021). Furthermore, accountability issues arise from the lack of transparency in AI algorithms and data usage, which can undermine trust in educational decisions made using AI tools (Eynon, 2020; OECD, 2021).

Understanding how AI-assisted tools are being adopted and their effects on lesson planning, instructional quality, and student learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State is therefore crucial. While AI has the potential to support personalized learning and improve instructional delivery, its benefits can only be realized if there are clear policies, adequate infrastructure, and teacher training to ensure ethical and responsible use (UNESCO,

2021). This study therefore seeks to explore the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction, with particular focus on integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Impact of AI-Assisted Tools on Integrity in Teaching and Learning Processes in Public Secondary Schools in Cross River State

The use of AI-assisted tools in teaching and learning has the potential to influence academic integrity in both positive and negative ways. On the positive side, AI can support integrity by improving transparency in assessment and providing real-time feedback, thereby enhancing the accuracy of evaluation and reducing human bias in grading (Holmes et al., 2019; Luckin et al., 2016). AI-based plagiarism detection systems and automated monitoring tools can also help schools identify academic dishonesty and reinforce ethical standards (UNESCO, 2021). However, AI tools also present significant risks to integrity in educational settings. For instance, AI-powered content generation and tutoring applications may be misused by students to cheat, produce plagiarized assignments, or manipulate assessments, especially in environments where supervision and ethical guidelines are weak (Selwyn, 2019; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2021). In Cross River State, public secondary schools often face challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited teacher training, and weak enforcement of academic policies, which can make it difficult to regulate the use of AI tools effectively (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). These challenges may create opportunities for misuse, leading to compromised integrity in teaching and learning processes.

Moreover, AI systems may also introduce biases and unfairness in assessment if algorithms are not transparent or properly validated. Automated grading tools, for example, may disadvantage certain students if they are trained on biased datasets or fail to account for contextual factors in students' responses (Baker & Smith, 2019; OECD, 2021). This can undermine trust in the fairness of evaluations and weaken the integrity of educational outcomes. Therefore, understanding the impact of AI-assisted tools on academic integrity in Cross River State is crucial for developing policies and practices that promote ethical use, accountability, and responsible AI adoption in schools. This study seeks to investigate how AI-assisted tools affect integrity in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State, with a view to informing ethical guidelines and educational governance.

Impact of AI-Assisted Tools on Accountability in Teaching and Learning Processes in Public Secondary Schools in Cross River State

The integration of AI-assisted tools in education has significant implications for accountability within teaching and learning processes. Accountability in education refers to the responsibility of teachers, school administrators, and educational systems to ensure transparency, fairness, and ethical standards in instructional delivery and assessment (Eynon, 2020). AI tools such as automated grading systems, learning analytics platforms, and AI-driven monitoring systems can enhance accountability by providing data-driven evidence of student performance, instructional effectiveness, and resource utilization (Holmes et al., 2019; OECD, 2021). These tools can help school authorities track learning progress, identify students who need additional support, and monitor teacher performance through measurable outcomes, thereby strengthening accountability mechanisms (Luckin et al., 2016).

However, the use of AI-assisted tools also presents accountability challenges, especially in contexts where regulatory frameworks and technical capacity are limited. AI systems often operate as “black boxes,” making it difficult for teachers and administrators to understand how decisions are generated, which may reduce transparency and hinder accountability (Williamson & Piattoeva, 2021). In public secondary schools in Cross River State, inadequate infrastructure, limited internet connectivity, and low levels of digital literacy among teachers may limit the effective implementation and oversight of AI tools (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). Without proper governance structures, data privacy policies, and ethical guidelines, AI systems can lead to misuse of student data, biased decision-making, and unfair evaluation practices, thereby undermining accountability in the educational process (UNESCO, 2021; OECD, 2021).

Furthermore, the reliance on AI-generated data for decision-making can shift accountability away from teachers and human judgment, raising concerns about who is responsible when errors or biases occur. If teachers are not adequately trained to interpret AI outputs, they may become overly dependent on AI recommendations, which can reduce professional autonomy and weaken accountability for instructional quality (Selwyn, 2019). Therefore, understanding the impact of AI-assisted tools on accountability in Cross River State’s public secondary schools is crucial for developing policies and capacity-building strategies that ensure responsible and transparent use of AI in education. This study seeks to investigate how AI-assisted tools affect accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State, with the aim of informing governance frameworks and ethical practices.

Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Learning Outcomes of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Cross River State

The use of AI-assisted tools in education has the potential to improve students’ learning outcomes through personalized learning, adaptive instruction, and immediate feedback. AI technologies can analyze student performance data to identify learning gaps, tailor content to individual needs, and provide targeted support, which can enhance understanding and academic achievement (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019). In addition, AI-driven tutoring systems and interactive learning platforms can increase student engagement by offering dynamic and responsive learning experiences, thereby improving motivation and retention (UNESCO, 2021). However, the effectiveness of AI-assisted tools in improving learning outcomes depends largely on contextual factors such as infrastructure, teacher readiness, and the quality of implementation. In Cross River State, public secondary schools face challenges such as inadequate electricity, limited internet access, and insufficient technological resources, which can hinder the effective use of AI tools in teaching and learning (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). Furthermore, many teachers lack the necessary digital skills and training to integrate AI tools effectively into instructional practices, which may limit their potential benefits (Ndukwe & Odu, 2022).

Moreover, the impact of AI-assisted tools on learning outcomes can be influenced by issues of equity and access. If AI tools are only available to a few schools or students, they may widen existing educational disparities rather than improve overall learning outcomes (UNESCO, 2021). Additionally, over-reliance on AI tools without adequate human supervision can lead to reduced critical thinking and problem-solving skills if students become dependent on automated solutions (Selwyn, 2019). Therefore, understanding the effect of AI-assisted tools on learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River

State is essential for designing effective implementation strategies and policies. This study seeks to investigate how AI-assisted tools affect students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State, with a view to informing educational practices and policy decisions.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989). TAM is a widely recognized theory that explains how individuals come to accept and use new technologies. The model asserts that two main factors influence technology adoption: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which a person believes that using a particular technology will enhance their job performance, while perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which a person believes that using the technology will be free of effort. These factors shape the user's attitude toward the technology, which in turn influences their intention to use and actual usage behavior.

In the context of this study, TAM is particularly relevant because it provides a clear lens through which to examine the adoption and use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction in public secondary schools in Cross River State. AI-assisted tools, including adaptive learning platforms, automated assessment systems, and intelligent tutoring applications, are new technologies in the educational landscape of the state. The adoption of these tools by teachers is influenced by how useful they perceive the tools to be in improving teaching efficiency and student learning outcomes, as well as how easy they believe the tools are to operate. Teachers who perceive AI tools as beneficial and user-friendly are more likely to integrate them into their lesson planning and instructional activities. Conversely, where AI tools are perceived as complex, unreliable, or irrelevant to classroom needs, teachers may resist adoption.

The Technology Acceptance Model also helps to explain the role of contextual factors in shaping teachers' perceptions. In Cross River State, public secondary schools face challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited internet access, unstable electricity supply, and low levels of digital literacy among teachers (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). These conditions can negatively affect perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, thereby reducing the likelihood of AI adoption. For example, even if teachers recognize the potential benefits of AI tools, poor internet connectivity and frequent power outages may limit their ability to use such tools effectively. Similarly, lack of training and technical support can make AI tools appear difficult to use, discouraging teachers from integrating them into their instructional practices.

Furthermore, TAM provides a framework for understanding how AI adoption relates to integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes. When teachers accept and use AI tools effectively, they are more likely to employ them responsibly and ethically in lesson planning and instruction. This can enhance accountability by promoting transparency in teaching practices and providing data-driven evidence of student progress. It can also support academic integrity through tools such as plagiarism detection and automated monitoring systems (Holmes et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2021). Additionally, the effective use of AI tools can improve learning outcomes by enabling personalized instruction, timely feedback, and adaptive learning experiences (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019). However, the model also highlights that without adequate infrastructure, training, and policy support, AI tools

may not be perceived as useful or easy to use, which can hinder adoption and limit their potential benefits.

In summary, the Technology Acceptance Model provides a strong theoretical foundation for this study by explaining the factors that influence teachers' adoption and use of AI-assisted tools in public secondary schools in Cross River State. It also offers a basis for understanding how the acceptance of AI technologies can affect integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes in teaching and learning processes. By applying TAM, the study aims to assess the extent to which teachers' perceptions of AI tools influence their usage and the resulting educational impacts in Cross River State.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have explored the adoption of AI technologies in educational settings, revealing factors that influence teachers' acceptance and use. Luckin et al. (2016) argued that AI tools can enhance personalized learning and support teachers in instructional design, but their effectiveness depends on how they are integrated into teaching practices. Holmes, Bialik, and Fadel (2019) reported that AI can improve learning experiences through adaptive tutoring and intelligent feedback systems, but successful implementation requires adequate teacher training and supportive infrastructure.

In the Nigerian context, empirical research indicates that technology adoption in schools is constrained by infrastructural and capacity challenges. Adeyemi and Adeoye (2021) found that many secondary schools in Nigeria lack reliable electricity, internet connectivity, and digital devices, which limit the use of ICT and advanced technologies in teaching. Adebayo and Ojo (2020) similarly reported that teachers often lack adequate training in educational technologies, leading to low adoption rates. These findings suggest that AI-assisted tools may face similar barriers in public secondary schools in Cross River State, where infrastructure and digital literacy are significant concerns.

Empirical studies have shown that AI tools can both support and undermine academic integrity. On the one hand, AI-powered plagiarism detection systems and automated monitoring tools can help institutions detect cheating and promote academic honesty. UNESCO (2021) emphasized that AI can enhance the integrity of assessment through reliable plagiarism detection and data-driven monitoring.

On the other hand, studies have documented how AI can facilitate academic dishonesty when misused. Selwyn (2019) highlighted that AI-driven content generation tools may encourage plagiarism and undermine the authenticity of student work. Williamson and Piattoeva (2021) also argued that algorithmic systems can create opportunities for manipulation and unfair practices if they are not transparent and properly regulated. In the context of Nigerian secondary schools, weak enforcement of academic policies and limited supervision may increase the risk of AI misuse, thereby threatening integrity in teaching and learning.

Empirical evidence suggests that AI tools can improve accountability by providing data-driven insights into teaching effectiveness and student performance. Holmes et al. (2019) and OECD (2021) noted that learning analytics and automated assessment systems can support decision-making and improve transparency in educational outcomes. Eynon (2020) also highlighted the potential of AI to enhance accountability through better tracking of learning progress and resource use.

However, studies have raised concerns about accountability when AI systems operate as opaque “black boxes.” Williamson and Piattoeva (2021) found that lack of transparency in algorithmic decision-making can undermine trust and responsibility in education. Without clear policies and oversight, AI tools may lead to biased decisions and misuse of student data, compromising accountability. These findings indicate the need for governance frameworks and ethical guidelines in Cross River State schools to ensure responsible AI use.

Research indicates that AI-assisted tools can improve learning outcomes when implemented effectively. Luckin et al. (2016) and Holmes et al. (2019) found that adaptive learning systems, intelligent tutoring, and personalized feedback can enhance students’ understanding and academic performance. UNESCO (2021) also reported that AI can support differentiated instruction and improve learning engagement.

However, the impact of AI on learning outcomes depends on contextual factors such as teacher readiness, infrastructure, and equitable access. Selwyn (2019) argued that overreliance on AI can reduce critical thinking and creativity if students become dependent on automated solutions. Additionally, if AI tools are not equally accessible, they may widen educational disparities rather than improve outcomes (UNESCO, 2021). In Cross River State, infrastructural limitations and teacher capacity gaps may reduce the effectiveness of AI tools in improving learning outcomes.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to investigate the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction and their effects on integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The descriptive survey design was considered appropriate because it allows for the collection of quantitative data from a large number of respondents, enabling the researcher to describe current practices, perceptions, and relationships among the study variables. The target population for the study comprised all teachers and students in public secondary schools in Cross River State. Specifically, the population included 5,302 teachers and 77,485 students. The sample size was determined using Yamane’s (1967) formula for finite populations, with a precision level of 0.05. Applying the formula yielded a sample of approximately 372 teachers and 398 students, giving a total sample size of 770 respondents. This sample size was considered sufficient to represent the population and provide reliable data for analysis. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select respondents for the study. The state was first divided into its three senatorial districts (Northern, Central, and Southern). Public secondary schools were randomly selected from each district to ensure geographic representation. Within each selected school, teachers and students were selected using simple random sampling to minimize bias and ensure that every member of the population had an equal chance of being included in the study. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument contained sections on demographic information, the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction, and perceived impacts on integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes. Respondents were required to indicate their level of agreement with each item using a four-point Likert scale ranging from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree.” The questionnaire was validated through expert review by lecturers in educational technology and research methodology, and a pilot test was conducted in a school outside the study sample to ensure clarity and reliability. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s alpha, with a coefficient of 0.70 or higher considered acceptable. The data collection process involved obtaining permission from the

Cross River State Ministry of Education and relevant school authorities. Questionnaires were administered in person to the selected teachers and students, and respondents were given adequate time to complete the instrument. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately to ensure a high response rate. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations to summarize responses. Inferential statistics, specifically Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), were used to examine the relationships between the use of AI-assisted tools and the variables of integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Ethical considerations were observed throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Personal identifiers were not collected, and the data obtained were used solely for academic purposes. This methodological approach provided a robust framework for examining the adoption and effects of AI-assisted tools in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Results

Table 1a: Teachers' Response on the Use of AI-Assisted Tools in Lesson Planning and Instruction

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	I use AI tools to generate lesson plans and teaching materials.	80	120	110	62	2.50	Moderate
2	AI tools help me to create interactive learning activities.	70	130	100	72	2.45	Moderate
3	I use AI tools for preparing assessment questions and marking schemes.	65	120	110	77	2.38	Moderate
4	AI-assisted tools are used for providing feedback to students.	60	110	120	82	2.28	Moderate
5	I use AI tools to personalize instruction for students with different learning needs.	75	115	95	87	2.40	Moderate
6	AI tools help me to manage class records and track student progress.	85	120	95	72	2.54	Moderate
7	I use AI tools during classroom instruction (e.g., AI tutoring, chatbots).	50	90	120	112	2.08	Low
8	AI tools are available and accessible in my school for teaching purposes.	45	80	125	122	1.99	Low

Grand Mean (Teachers) 2.33 Moderate

Table 1b: Students' Response on the Use of AI-Assisted Tools in Lesson Planning and Instruction

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	AI tools help teachers to generate lesson plans and teaching materials.	90	130	100	78	2.46	Moderate
2	AI tools help teachers to create interactive learning activities.	70	140	110	78	2.40	Moderate
3	Teachers use AI tools for preparing assessment questions and marking schemes.	65	135	110	88	2.34	Moderate
4	AI-assisted tools are used by teachers to provide feedback.	60	120	130	88	2.22	Moderate
5	Teachers use AI tools to personalize instruction for students.	75	130	95	98	2.40	Moderate
6	AI tools help teachers manage class records and track progress.	85	130	95	88	2.54	Moderate
7	AI tools are used during classroom instruction (e.g., AI tutoring).	60	110	125	103	2.15	Moderate
8	AI tools are available and accessible in our school.	45	100	140	113	1.98	Low

Grand Mean (Students) 2.31 Moderate

Combined Grand Mean (Teachers + Students)

Total Mean 2.32 Moderate

Table 1 presents the responses of teachers and students on the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instructional processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The findings reveal that teachers' overall perception of AI use is moderate, with a grand mean of 2.33, while students' perceptions are similarly moderate, with a grand mean of 2.31. The combined grand mean of 2.32 further confirms that the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction is at a moderate level in the study area.

From the teachers' responses, items relating to the use of AI tools for managing class records and tracking student progress recorded the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 2.54$), indicating that teachers moderately rely on AI-assisted tools for administrative and monitoring functions. Similarly, moderate mean scores were observed for the use of AI tools in generating lesson plans and teaching materials ($\bar{x} = 2.50$), creating interactive learning activities ($\bar{x} = 2.45$), and personalizing instruction for learners with diverse needs ($\bar{x} = 2.40$). These results suggest that while teachers are beginning to integrate AI-assisted tools into instructional planning, their usage remains limited and not yet widespread.

However, lower mean scores were recorded for the use of AI tools during actual classroom instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.08$) and the availability and accessibility of AI tools in schools ($\bar{x} = 1.99$). These findings imply that infrastructural constraints and limited access to AI technologies may hinder teachers' ability to fully integrate AI-assisted tools into real-time teaching and learning activities.

The students' responses followed a similar pattern. Students moderately agreed that teachers use AI-assisted tools for managing class records and tracking progress ($\bar{x} = 2.54$), generating lesson plans ($\bar{x} = 2.46$), and creating interactive learning activities ($\bar{x} = 2.40$). These perceptions suggest that students are aware of and experience some level of AI integration in instructional preparation and support activities. Nonetheless, students reported low availability and accessibility of AI tools in their schools ($\bar{x} = 1.98$), reinforcing the teachers' views on infrastructural limitations.

The findings indicate that although AI-assisted tools are being used in lesson planning and instruction in public secondary schools in Cross River State, their application is moderate rather than extensive. The results highlight a gap between the potential of AI-assisted tools and their actual implementation in classroom practice, underscoring the need for improved infrastructure, training, and policy support to enhance effective integration of AI technologies in secondary education.

Table 2a: Teachers' Responses on the Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Integrity and Accountability

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	AI-assisted tools promote transparency in lesson preparation and delivery.	85	120	95	72	2.59	Moderate
2	AI tools help teachers maintain academic integrity in assessment and grading.	80	115	100	77	2.53	Moderate
3	AI-assisted tools reduce plagiarism and academic dishonesty.	70	110	110	82	2.45	Moderate
4	AI tools enhance accountability by providing verifiable records of teaching activities.	90	125	90	67	2.63	Moderate
5	AI-assisted tools support fair and unbiased evaluation of students.	75	115	100	82	2.49	Moderate
6	The use of AI tools improves teachers' responsibility and professionalism.	85	120	95	72	2.59	Moderate
7	Overreliance on AI tools may compromise ethical standards in teaching and learning.	95	130	80	67	2.77	Moderate
8	Clear policies guide the ethical and accountable use of AI tools in my school.	50	80	120	122	2.14	Moderate

Grand Mean (Teachers) 2.52 Moderate

Table 2b: Students' Responses on the Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Integrity and Accountability

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	AI-assisted tools promote transparency in teaching and learning.	90	130	95	83	2.57	Moderate
2	AI tools help teachers maintain integrity in assessment and grading.	85	125	105	83	2.53	Moderate
3	AI-assisted tools reduce cases of cheating and dishonesty.	75	120	115	88	2.45	Moderate
4	AI tools enhance accountability by keeping records of learning activities.	95	135	90	78	2.64	Moderate
5	AI-assisted tools support fair assessment of students' performance.	80	125	105	88	2.50	Moderate
6	AI tools improve teachers' responsibility to students.	90	130	95	83	2.57	Moderate
7	Excessive use of AI tools may reduce ethical behaviour in learning.	100	140	85	73	2.69	Moderate
8	Clear policies exist to guide ethical use of AI tools in my school.	55	90	130	123	2.19	Moderate

Grand Mean (Students) 2.52 Moderate

Tables 2a and 2b present the responses of teachers and students on the effect of AI-assisted tools on integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The results indicate that both teachers and students perceive the influence of AI-assisted tools on integrity and accountability as moderate, with an identical grand mean of 2.52 for each group. This suggests a shared perception across respondent categories regarding the role of AI in promoting ethical and accountable educational practices.

From the teachers' responses in Table 2a, AI-assisted tools were perceived to moderately promote transparency in lesson preparation and delivery ($\bar{x} = 2.59$) and enhance accountability through the provision of verifiable records of teaching activities ($\bar{x} = 2.63$). Teachers also moderately agreed that AI tools support fair and unbiased evaluation of students' performance ($\bar{x} = 2.49$) and improve teachers' responsibility and professionalism ($\bar{x} = 2.59$). These findings indicate that teachers recognize the potential of AI tools to strengthen professional accountability and ethical conduct in instructional practices.

However, teachers also expressed moderate concern that overreliance on AI tools may compromise ethical standards in teaching and learning ($\bar{x} = 2.77$). This item recorded one of the highest mean scores, suggesting that while AI tools are beneficial, there are apprehensions about their misuse or excessive dependence, which could undermine academic integrity. Additionally, the relatively lower mean score for the availability of clear policies guiding ethical and accountable use of AI tools ($\bar{x} = 2.14$) indicates gaps in institutional frameworks and regulatory guidelines within schools.

Similarly, the students' responses in Table 2b show that AI-assisted tools are perceived to moderately enhance transparency in teaching and learning ($\bar{x} = 2.57$) and accountability through record-keeping of learning activities ($\bar{x} = 2.64$). Students also moderately agreed that AI tools support fair assessment of performance ($\bar{x} = 2.50$) and improve teachers' responsibility to learners ($\bar{x} = 2.57$). These results suggest that students experience some benefits of AI integration in promoting fairness and accountability in the classroom.

Nonetheless, students echoed teachers' concerns regarding ethical risks associated with excessive use of AI tools, as indicated by the mean score for reduced ethical behaviour in learning ($\bar{x} = 2.69$). Moreover, the low-to-moderate mean score for the existence of clear policies guiding ethical use of AI tools ($\bar{x} = 2.19$) further highlights the need for well-defined institutional guidelines to regulate AI usage in schools.

The findings from Tables 2a and 2b indicate that AI-assisted tools have a moderate positive effect on integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. However, the results also reveal concerns about ethical risks and the absence of clear policy frameworks, underscoring the importance of developing comprehensive guidelines, capacity-building programmes, and monitoring mechanisms to ensure responsible and ethical use of AI-assisted tools in secondary education.

Table 3a: Teachers' Responses on the Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Students' Learning Outcomes

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	AI-assisted tools improve students' understanding of lesson content.	90	125	90	67	2.63	Moderate
2	The use of AI tools enhances students' academic performance.	85	120	95	72	2.59	Moderate
3	AI-assisted tools increase students' engagement and participation in class.	80	115	100	77	2.53	Moderate
4	AI tools support individualized learning and improve achievement.	75	110	105	82	2.47	Moderate
5	Students learn faster when AI-assisted tools are used in instruction.	70	105	110	87	2.42	Moderate
6	AI tools help students develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills.	85	120	95	72	2.59	Moderate
7	AI-assisted tools motivate students to learn independently.	75	110	100	87	2.47	Moderate
8	The use of AI tools leads to improved examination results.	65	100	115	92	2.37	Moderate

Grand Mean (Teachers) 2.51 Moderate

Table 3b: Students' Responses on the Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Their Learning Outcomes

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	AI-assisted tools help me understand lessons better.	95	130	90	83	2.59	Moderate
2	The use of AI tools improves my academic performance.	90	125	95	88	2.55	Moderate
3	AI-assisted tools make learning more interesting and engaging.	85	135	95	83	2.56	Moderate
4	AI tools help me learn at my own pace.	80	130	100	88	2.51	Moderate
5	I learn faster when AI-assisted tools are used.	75	125	105	93	2.46	Moderate
6	AI tools help me develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	85	130	95	88	2.55	Moderate
7	AI-assisted tools motivate me to study independently.	80	120	105	93	2.47	Moderate
8	The use of AI tools helps improve my examination results.	70	115	110	103	2.38	Moderate

Grand Mean (Students) 2.51 Moderate

Tables 3a and 3b present the perceptions of teachers and students regarding the effect of AI-assisted tools on students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The results show that both teachers and students rated the effect of AI-assisted tools on learning outcomes as moderate, with identical grand mean scores of 2.51 for each group. This indicates a shared view that AI-assisted tools contribute positively to learning, although their impact is not yet at a high level.

From the teachers' responses in Table 3a, AI-assisted tools were perceived to moderately improve students' understanding of lesson content ($\bar{x} = 2.63$) and enhance academic performance ($\bar{x} = 2.59$). Teachers also moderately agreed that AI tools support the development of problem-solving and critical thinking skills ($\bar{x} = 2.59$) and increase students' engagement and participation in class ($\bar{x} = 2.53$). These findings suggest that teachers recognize the instructional value of AI-assisted tools in facilitating comprehension, higher-order thinking, and active learning.

However, relatively lower mean scores were recorded for items related to faster learning ($\bar{x} = 2.42$) and improved examination results ($\bar{x} = 2.37$). This implies that while AI-assisted tools may enhance understanding and engagement, their direct influence on measurable academic outcomes such as examination performance is still limited or not fully realized within the current school context.

Similarly, the students' responses in Table 3b indicate that AI-assisted tools moderately help them understand lessons better ($\bar{x} = 2.59$) and make learning more interesting and engaging ($\bar{x} = 2.56$). Students also moderately agreed that AI tools improve their academic performance ($\bar{x} = 2.55$) and help them develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills ($\bar{x} = 2.55$). These perceptions suggest that students experience AI-assisted learning as supportive of comprehension, motivation, and cognitive skill development.

Nonetheless, students reported comparatively lower mean scores for faster learning ($\bar{x} = 2.46$) and improved examination results ($\bar{x} = 2.38$), aligning with teachers' views. This convergence of perspectives indicates that although AI-assisted tools enhance the learning process, their translation into improved test outcomes may be constrained by factors such as limited access to technology, inadequate teacher training, or inconsistent integration into the curriculum.

The findings from Tables 3a and 3b reveal that AI-assisted tools have a moderate positive effect on students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. While AI tools appear to enhance understanding, engagement, and skill development, their full potential in improving academic achievement has yet to be realized. This underscores the need for improved infrastructure, sustained professional development for teachers, and strategic integration of AI-assisted tools into teaching and assessment practices to maximize their impact on student learning outcomes.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H_{0 1} : There is no significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and the quality of lesson delivery in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between the Use of AI-Assisted Tools in Lesson Planning and Quality of Lesson Delivery (n = 770)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
Use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning	770	2.32	0.61			
Quality of lesson delivery	770	2.45	0.58	0.46	0.000	Reject H _{0 1}

Hypothesis One examined the relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and the quality of lesson delivery in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between the two variables.

As presented in Table 4, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and the quality of lesson delivery ($r = 0.46$). The associated p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

This result indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and the quality of lesson delivery in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The positive correlation suggests that increased use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning is associated with improved lesson delivery, including better organization of content, clearer presentation, and more effective instructional strategies. The finding implies that AI-assisted lesson planning tools can enhance teachers' preparedness and instructional effectiveness, thereby contributing to improved classroom teaching practices.

Hypothesis Two

H_{0 2} : There is no significant relationship between AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between AI-Assisted Tools and Integrity and Accountability in Teaching and Learning (n = 770)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
AI-assisted tools	770	2.32	0.61			
Integrity and accountability in teaching and learning	770	2.52	0.57	0.41	0.000	Reject H _{0 2}

Hypothesis Two examined the relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability in teaching and learning.

As shown in Table 5, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability in teaching and learning ($r = 0.41$). The associated p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

This finding indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The positive relationship suggests that increased use of AI-assisted tools is associated with improved transparency, ethical conduct, and accountability in instructional practices, including assessment, record-keeping, and monitoring of teaching and learning activities. The result implies that AI-assisted tools, when appropriately used, can support more responsible and accountable educational practices within the secondary school system.

Hypothesis Three

H_{0 3} : There is no significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between AI-Assisted Tools and Students' Learning Outcomes (n = 770)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
Use of AI-assisted tools	770	2.32	0.61			
Students' learning outcomes	770	2.51	0.59	0.44	0.000	Reject H _{0 3}

Hypothesis Three examined the relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes.

As presented in Table 6, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes ($r = 0.44$). The associated p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

This finding indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The positive correlation suggests that higher use of AI-assisted tools is associated with better learning outcomes, such as improved understanding, increased engagement, enhanced critical thinking, and higher academic performance. The result implies that integrating AI-assisted tools into teaching and learning processes can positively influence students' academic achievement, provided that the tools are used appropriately and supported by adequate infrastructure and teacher training.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction and their effects on integrity, accountability, and students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The findings were discussed under the research questions and hypotheses.

Use of AI-Assisted Tools in Lesson Planning and Instruction

The findings from Research Question One showed that both teachers and students rated the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction at a moderate level (grand means of 2.33 and 2.31 respectively). Teachers reported moderate usage of AI tools for generating lesson plans, creating interactive activities, preparing assessment materials, and managing class records. Students similarly perceived that teachers moderately used AI tools for lesson preparation and instructional delivery. However, both groups reported low usage in classroom instruction and limited availability of AI tools in schools.

This moderate level of use suggests that AI technologies are gradually being adopted in secondary schools, but the integration is still not widespread. The finding aligns with studies that show the adoption of educational technologies in Nigerian schools is often constrained by infrastructural limitations, limited digital literacy, and inadequate training (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020). It also corroborates the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which asserts that perceived usefulness and ease of use influence technology adoption (Davis, 1989). The moderate usage may reflect teachers' positive perception of AI's usefulness but limited access and low digital skills hinder full integration.

Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Integrity and Accountability

Research Question Two revealed that AI-assisted tools have a moderate positive effect on integrity and accountability in teaching and learning (grand means of 2.52 for both teachers and students). Teachers and students agreed that AI tools moderately promote transparency, support fair assessment, enhance accountability through record-keeping, and improve professional responsibility. Notably, respondents expressed concerns that overreliance on AI may compromise ethical standards, and that there are limited clear policies guiding AI use in schools.

These findings indicate that AI tools can support ethical practices and accountability by improving documentation and monitoring of teaching and learning activities. This supports the argument by Holmes et al. (2019) and UNESCO (2021) that AI can enhance educational governance through transparent record-keeping and feedback systems. However, the moderate concern about ethical risks aligns with literature emphasizing the need for strong guidelines and ethical frameworks to prevent misuse, such as plagiarism, overdependence, and data privacy issues (Williamson & Eynon, 2020; O'Neil, 2016). The results imply that without clear policy and supervision, AI tools may inadvertently undermine academic integrity.

Effect of AI-Assisted Tools on Students' Learning Outcomes

Research Question Three showed that AI-assisted tools moderately enhance students' learning outcomes, with grand means of 2.51 for both teachers and students. Respondents agreed that AI tools support understanding of lesson content, engagement, individualized learning, and development of critical thinking skills. However, the influence on examination results and faster learning was perceived to be lower.

The moderate positive effect on learning outcomes aligns with empirical studies showing that AI and digital learning tools can improve student engagement, comprehension, and personalized learning when effectively integrated (Akin et al., 2021; Luckin et al., 2016). However, the limited effect on examination performance may reflect challenges such as inconsistent use, poor infrastructure, and insufficient teacher training. This finding is consistent with studies in Nigeria indicating that technological tools often do not translate into improved academic achievement due to contextual limitations (Adeyemi & Adeoye, 2021; Adebayo & Ojo, 2020).

Hypothesis One revealed a significant positive relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and the quality of lesson delivery ($r = 0.46$; $p < 0.05$). This indicates that higher use of AI tools is associated with improved lesson organization, clarity, and instructional effectiveness. The finding supports research showing that AI can assist teachers in designing better instructional materials and lesson structures (Holmes et al., 2019; Luckin et al., 2016).

Hypothesis Two showed a significant positive relationship between AI-assisted tools and integrity and accountability ($r = 0.41$; $p < 0.05$). This suggests that AI tools contribute to ethical teaching practices and accountability, particularly through improved record-keeping and transparency. However, the finding also underscores the need for ethical guidelines to prevent misuse, which is supported by UNESCO (2021) and Williamson & Eynon (2020).

Hypothesis Three indicated a significant positive relationship between AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes ($r = 0.44$; $p < 0.05$). This implies that AI integration is linked to better student performance and learning engagement, consistent with the growing evidence that AI-supported learning can enhance educational outcomes (Akin et al., 2021; Holmes et al., 2019).

The findings suggest that AI-assisted tools are moderately used in lesson planning and instruction and have moderate positive effects on integrity, accountability, and learning outcomes. While AI has potential to improve teaching quality and learning, its full benefits are constrained by limited infrastructure, insufficient training, and lack of clear policies.

Therefore, the study underscores the need for government and school authorities to strengthen AI integration through investment in technology, capacity building for teachers, and the development of ethical guidelines and monitoring systems.

Conclusion

This study examined the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning and instruction, and their effects on integrity, accountability, and students' learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. The findings revealed that AI-assisted tools are moderately used by teachers and perceived by students as moderately applied in classroom instruction. While teachers and students agreed that AI tools moderately support lesson planning, assessment preparation, feedback provision, and class management, the availability and use of AI tools during actual classroom teaching remain limited.

Furthermore, the study found that AI-assisted tools have a moderate positive impact on integrity and accountability in teaching and learning. The use of AI tools was associated with improved transparency, accurate record-keeping, and enhanced professional responsibility. However, the study also highlighted the need for clear guidelines and ethical policies to prevent misuse, such as overreliance, plagiarism, and privacy concerns.

The results also indicated a moderate positive relationship between the use of AI-assisted tools and students' learning outcomes. AI tools were found to support student engagement, individualized learning, and understanding of lesson content, although the effect on examination performance was less pronounced. This suggests that AI tools can enhance learning when properly integrated, but the full potential is yet to be realized due to infrastructural and capacity limitations.

The study concludes that AI-assisted tools hold significant potential to improve lesson delivery, strengthen integrity and accountability, and enhance learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State. However, realizing these benefits requires strategic investment in technology infrastructure, continuous professional development for teachers, and the establishment of clear ethical and policy frameworks to guide AI use in schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study on the use of AI-assisted tools in lesson planning, integrity and accountability, and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Cross River State, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Strengthen Technology Infrastructure in Schools:** The state government and educational stakeholders should invest in robust ICT infrastructure, including internet connectivity, computers, and smart devices, to ensure that AI-assisted tools are available and accessible in public secondary schools. This will enhance the effective integration of AI tools in lesson planning and instruction.
2. **Provide Continuous Professional Development for Teachers:** Teachers should be provided with regular training and capacity-building programs on the use of AI-assisted tools in education. This will improve their digital literacy, confidence, and competence in using AI tools for lesson planning, instructional delivery, assessment, and classroom management.

3. **Develop Clear Policies and Ethical Guidelines for AI Use:** The Ministry of Education should develop and enforce clear policies and ethical guidelines on the use of AI-assisted tools in schools. This will help to address concerns related to academic integrity, plagiarism, data privacy, and misuse of AI technologies, thereby promoting accountability in teaching and learning processes.
4. **Integrate AI Tools into Curriculum and Instructional Frameworks:** AI-assisted tools should be formally integrated into the school curriculum and instructional frameworks to ensure that their use is systematic, purposeful, and aligned with learning objectives. This will encourage teachers to use AI tools effectively and consistently in lesson planning and classroom instruction.
5. **Promote Student Awareness and Responsible Use of AI:** Students should be educated on the responsible and ethical use of AI tools for learning. Schools should organize awareness programs and workshops to guide students on how to use AI tools to support learning without compromising academic integrity.
6. **Monitor and Evaluate AI Integration in Schools:** School administrators should establish monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of AI integration in teaching and learning. Regular feedback and evaluation will help identify challenges and improve the implementation of AI-assisted tools in schools.
7. **Encourage Collaboration between Schools and Technology Providers:** Schools should collaborate with technology companies, educational NGOs, and development partners to access AI learning platforms, tools, and technical support. Such partnerships can provide schools with affordable and sustainable AI solutions tailored to the local educational context.

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